

Documentation Peru

Interest Group

Guidelines

International Committee for Documentation of the ICOM
(ICOM DOCUMENTATION)

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DOCUMENTATION

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Foundations

The interest in the documentation of movable heritage was the starting point for the formation of the *Documentation Peru Interest Group*, which has the guidance and support of the ICOM International Committee for Documentation (ICOM DOCUMENTATION). This initiative arises from a group of Peruvian professionals linked to the field of cultural heritage, under the concept of “[interest group](#)”, a term used to define a *group of people organized around a common interest, with the purpose of acting jointly in defence of this interest*. Considering that few people within the Peruvian museum community are affiliated with ICOM or ICOM DOCUMENTATION, it was decided to form an interest group, so that participation in the activities carried out by this group is not limited to members of the two mentioned organizations.

The *Documentation Peru Interest Group* believes that its work should be carried out from a [glocal perspective](#). For this purpose, it will take into consideration the recommendations and documents generated by international organizations linked to cultural heritage and museums, such as the [ICOM Code of Ethics for Museums](#), which in subsection 2.20 states:

Museum collections should be documented according to accepted professional standards. Such documentation should include a full identification and description of each item, its associations, provenance, condition, treatment and present location. Such data should be kept in a secure environment and be supported by retrieval systems providing access to the information by the museum personnel and other legitimate users (ICOM, 2017, p. 14).

We will also consider the recommendations of the ICOM Ethics Committee ([ETHCOM, 2020](#)), the postulates, standards, and guidelines of the ICOM International Documentation Committee ([ICOM – CIDOC](#)), and the [Statement of principles of museum documentation CIDOC, versión 6.2 \(2012\)](#). For the definition of guidelines at the local level, we will add to the previous ones: [Ley General del Patrimonio Cultural de la Nación N° 28296](#) (General Law of Peruvian Cultural Heritage) and [Estándares para la Gestión de Colecciones de Spectrum aplicado al contexto del Perú](#) (translation of the Spectrum Collection Management Standards applied to the Peruvian context).

The Group also seeks to participate in ICOM DOCUMENTATION initiatives and, in this regard, will collaborate with the [Domino Working Group](#) (DocumentandO Museu Iberoamericano), which addresses documentation at the Ibero-American scope.

General Objective

Promote good practices in heritage documentation that reflect 21st-century documentation (use of standards and implementation of rules for using these models; use —as far as possible— a controlled vocabulary).

Specific Objectives

1. Describe the current situation regarding the documentation of movable cultural heritage in museum institutions in Peru.
2. Promote the use of a controlled vocabulary based on existing thesauri ([TAA](#), [Tesauro PC España](#), [Tesauro Regional Patrimonial](#), [Tesauro Getty](#)) or through the use of proposed alternatives for structuring data ([WikiData](#), from the [Fundación Wikimedia](#)).
3. Establish rules for the use of descriptive categories in the documentation of cultural and natural heritage assets, based on an evaluation of their current use and their equivalence with existing standards.
4. Develop joint actions with the DOMINO Working Group, to promote the knowledge exchange among professionals in Ibero-America.
5. Disseminate ICOM DOCUMENTATION's tools, guides, guidelines, and perspectives on heritage documentation in museums.

Actions

The actions on which the group will focus will be established annually:

- Contribute to the implementation of the DOMINO Working Group study: DOCUMENTATION IN IBEROAMERICAN MUSEUMS 2025.
- Disseminate ICOM DOCUMENTATION's tools, guides, guidelines and perspectives on documentation in museums.

About Members ([Agreements](#))

It is made up of a national community —open, not limited to members of ICOM or CIDOC— of people who work directly or indirectly with heritage collections, funds, and patrimony or in museum institutions, and whose common interest is oriented toward the practice and/or problems of heritage documentation at its different levels.

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